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Research Article

Nitrate Contamination of Public Drinking Water Sources in Shendi Locality, River Nile State Sudan

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ABSTRACT

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the locality of Shendi, River Nile state, Sudan to determine the concentration of nitrates in drinking water and its potential health risk on consumers. Using random sampling technique 44 drinking water sources were selected for the purpose of this study. Data were collected directly from the field by; sanitary survey and nitrate analysis of drinking water sources. Of these points 15.9% were found to have elevated nitrate level (excess 10 ml/l). Nitrate concentration was found to be highest among ground water sources. Anthropogenic sources were the ones that most often cause the amount of nitrate to rise to a dangerous level in this area. Four (57.1%) of the sources which have excess level of nitrate were exposed to latrine contamination and 3 (40.1%) of the sources which were highly contaminated with nitrate also exposed to more than one sources of contaminations: septic tank, soakage pits and animal manure. The study concluded that the anthropogenic sources are really the ones that most often cause the amount of nitrate to rise to a dangerous level, and there are high potentiality of public health problems in areas where nitrate concentrations elevated, specifically the risk of methemoglobinemia, increased incidence of certain cancers, and increased birth defects.

Keywords: Nitrate, Nitrate contamination, Drinking water and Anthropogenic sources.

INTRODUCTION

Nitrates are known as a sanitary chemical (Free ammonia, albuminoid ammonia, nitrites, and nitrates) which result from decomposition of organic matter (Guideline for Drinking-Water Quality (WHO, 1997). Nitrate in groundwater may result from point sources such as sewage disposal systems and livestock facilities, from nonpoint sources such as fertilized cropland, parks, golf courses, lawns, and gardens, or from naturally occurring sources of nitrogen (Nebraska-lincoln University and CUSDA, 2008). Nitrates are stable, and their presence shows remote pollution (WHO, 1997).

Nitrate pollution of surface and groundwater has become a major ecological problem in some agricultural areas. Although fertilizer in runoff is most often blamed, there is evidence that concentration of livestock in feedlots is now the major source of agricultural nitrate pollution (U.S. Geological Survey, 1993). The main source of nitrate pollution in the groundwater results from the actions of farmers (Behm, 1989). The farmers first deplete the soil by "excessive, repeat planting" and then try to replenish the resulting less-productive soil by putting more and more nitrogen-based fertilizer on the land in an attempt to keep crop yields constant. The presence of nitrate and nitrite in water may result from the excessive application of fertilizers or from leaching of wastewater or other organic waste into surface water and ground water (WHO, 1997).

The anthropogenic sources are really the ones that most often cause the amount of nitrate to rise to a dangerous level. Waste materials are one of the anthropogenic sources of nitrate contamination of groundwater. Many local sources of potential nitrate contamination of groundwater exist such as, "sites used for disposal of human and animal sewage; industrial wastes ... (Vogt and Cotruvo, 1987); and sites where handling and accidental spills of nitrogenous materials may accumulate". Septic tanks are another example of anthropogenic source nitrogen contamination of the groundwater. Many areas of the United States and other countries have reported significant contamination of groundwater from septic tanks. Ground water contamination is usually related to the density of septic systems (Hallberg and Keeney, 1993).

Public drinking water standards established by EPA fall into two categories — Secondary Standards and Primary Standards. Secondary Standards are based on aesthetic factors such as taste, odor, color, corrosivity, foaming, and staining properties of water that may affect the suitability of a water supply for drinking and other domestic uses. Primary Standards are based on health considerations and are designed to protect human health. The EPA Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) is measured and reported as nitrate-nitrogen, (NO₃-N), which is the amount of nitrogen in the nitrate form. Milligrams per liter (mg/L) is the same as parts per million (ppm) (Mueller et al., 1995). The EPA Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) for nitrate-nitrogen in a public water supply is 10 milligrams per liter (mg/L) which can also be expressed as 10 parts per million (ppm), and is based on acute health effects, specifically the risk of methaemoglobinemia (blue- baby' syndrome) (Burkart and Kolpin, 1993).

Excess nitrate in drinking-water has been linked to methaemoglobinemia in infants, Although nitrate generally is not an adult public-health threat, ingestion in drinking water by infants can cause low oxygen levels in the blood, a potentially fatal condition (Spalding and Exner, 1993). The water responsible (for "Blue babies") has had nitrates in excess of 10 mg/l. Nitrate leads to the oxidation of normal hemoglobin to methaemoglobin which is unable to transport oxygen to the tissues. For this reason, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has established a drinking-water standard (Maximum Contamination Limit "MCL" for nitrate in water is 10 parts per million) (American Public Health Association et al., 1992) of 10 milligrams per liter (mg/L) nitrate as nitrogen (Mueller et al., 1995).

Some studies have shown a correlation between long-term ingestion of elevated nitrate and increased incidence of certain cancers, and increased birth defects.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This observational study was designed as cross-sectional study and conducted in the locality of Shendi, River Nile, Sudan. Shendi locality depends upon agriculture for food and for the income from cash crops. Animal husbandry (cattle, sheep, goats and camels) is practiced both by the few nomadic and the settled farmers. The locality is faced with a lot of problems; the greatest are sanitation and drinking water quality, as Omer and Sallam (2012) reported that about 27.1% of the drinking water sources were contaminated with E coli and contribute to an increased incidence of water-borne diseases. The aims of this study is to determine the concentration of nitrates as sanitary chemical in drinking water and its potential health risk on consumers.

The study population involved all drinking water sources in the towns and the villages of the locality. Proportional stratified sampling allocation was followed to select the sample size of 44 drinking water sources for the purposes of this study. The data of the study was directly collected from the field by; sanitary survey and nitrate analysis for the collected samples of drinking water sources.

The spectrophotometric method measuring absorbance of nitrate at 410 nm was used to measure the nitrate concentration levels for the samples. Nitrates levels are reported in mg/L nitrate (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 1995; Standard Method, 2002).

The collected data had been analyzed by computer; using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 18.0. Frequency, percentages, cross tabulation associations and differences between means of/ and among samples variables were calculated and compared using X² and Fisher's exact tests: a P-value of < 0.05 indicates statistical significance.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that drinking water sources in Shendi locality were exposed to different levels of nitrate contamination, 15.9% of the drinking water sources were significantly contaminated with nitrate, that their nitrate level are greater than the maximum contamination limit "MCL" for nitrate in public drinking water (10 parts per million or 10 mg/l). Of the contaminated sources 28.6 % (2/7) are shallow wells and 71.4% (5/7) are deep boreholes. The types of drinking water sources were very significantly difference considering nitrate level, significant contamination were found among the groundwater (*P-value =0.036*).

As shown in table 2, although excess nitrate levels in drinking-water source was not statistically significance with their surrounding source of contamination (*P-value =0.721*), but these levels seems to be influenced by these anthropogenic sources of contamination. That 57.1% (4) of the sources which have excess level of nitrate were exposed to latrine contamination. 40.1% (3) of the sources which were highly contaminated with nitrate also exposed to the more than one of the following sources of contaminations: septic tank, soakage pits and animal manure...etc.

Table 1: Nitrate level ml/L among various types of drinking water sources in Shendi locality

Type of drinking water source	Nitrate Level ml/L		Total
	Less than 10 ml/L	Excess of 10 ml/L	
Shallow well	(2.7%) 01	(28.6%) 2	3
Deep Bore hole	(59.5%) 22	(71.4%) 5	27
Nile station	(100%)11	(0.0%)0	11
Hand pump well	(100%)03	(0.0%)0	3
Total	37	7	44

$$p = 0.036 < 0.05$$

Table 2: Association between nitrate level and surrounding anthropogenic nitrogen contamination of the drinking water sources in Shendi locality

Type of contamination to which drinking water sources exposed	Nitrate Level ml/L		Total
	Less than 10 ml/L	Excess of 10 ml/L	
VIP Latrine	(40.5%) 15	(57.1%) 4	19
Septic tank or soakage pits	(8.1%) 3	(14.3%) 1	4
Animal manure	(100%)1	(0.0%)0	11
More than one of the above sources	(48.6%) 18	(28.6%)2	20
Total	(100) 37	(100) 7	44

$$p = 0.721 > 0.05$$

DISCUSSION

Drinking water sources showed a very significant difference of concentration level for nitrate as NO_3 mg/l. It was found to be highest among the ground water sources (Table1). 15.9% (7) of the sources exceed the nitrate maximum contamination limit for drinking-water standard which was established by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), (1995). Also the nitrate level in these sources of drinking water exceed 10 milligrams per liter (mg/L) nitrate (10 parts per million) as determined by American Public Health Association et al. (2002). The excess nitrate level can inhibit growth, impair the immune system as Melian et al. (1997) reviewed that raised nitrate is a potential public health problem in countries where concentrations in groundwater reach extremely high values. Guideline for Drinking-Water Quality-Training Pack (WHO, 1997), also reported that; acute effects may be encountered where levels of certain chemical are high from natural sources, such as...nitrate. The water responsible for "Blue babies" has had nitrates in excess of 10 mg/l.

The nitrate levels in drinking water sources although statistically not significant, but seems to be influenced by the sources of contamination to which they are exposed to (table 2), the sources which were highly contaminated with nitrate also exposed to the more than one of the following sources of contaminations: septic tank, soakage pits and animal manure...etc. This result was the same with the one reported by WHO (1997) that the presence of nitrate in water may result from the excessive application of fertilizers or from leaching of wastewater or other organic waste into surface water and ground water. Also the result goes with what Vomocil (1987); and Hallberg and Keeney (1993) reported that; many local sources of potential nitrate contamination of groundwater exist such as, "sites used for disposal of human and animal sewage; industrial wastes related to food processing, munitions, and some polyresin facilities and sites where handling and accidental spills of nitrogenous materials may accumulate." Nebraska-lincoln University and CUSDA (2008) also reported that nitrate in groundwater may result from point sources such as sewage disposal systems and livestock facilities, from nonpoint sources such as fertilized cropland, parks, golf courses, lawns, and gardens, or from naturally occurring sources of nitrogen.

CONCLUSION

Many drinking water sources in Shendi were highly contaminated with nitrate, which elevated than the EPA Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) for a public water supply (10 milligrams per liter (mg/L)). Nitrate contamination was found to be highest among the ground water sources. Also the drinking water sources in Shendi were exposed to more than one of the following anthropogenic sources of contaminations: septic tank, soakage pits and animal manure, which could lead to the nitrate concentrations elevated.

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